

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS ACCORDING TO CULTURAL FEATURES

(on the example of the theme “Marriage”)

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Abstract. *Language is a cultural system's arbitrary and customary symbolic resource. While it identifies speakers' various beliefs and worldviews, it also causes a lot of conflict in communication. As a result, academics have long strived to comprehend the function of language in human communication. To investigate language and culture, communication scholars, as well as those from other disciplines (e.g., linguistics, anthropology, psychology, and sociology), depend on each other's work.*

Keywords: *phraseology, phraseological units, concept, linguoculturemes, nominative phraseological units, communicative phraseological units.*

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ АНГЛИЙСКИХ И УЗБЕКСКИХ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ

(на примере темы «Брак»)

Аннотация. *Язык является произвольным и привычным символическим ресурсом культурной системы. Хотя он идентифицирует различные убеждения и мировоззрения говорящих, он также вызывает множество конфликтов в общении. В результате ученые уже давно стремятся понять функцию языка в человеческом общении. При исследовании языка и культуры ученые, занимающиеся коммуникацией, а также представители других дисциплин (например, лингвистики, антропологии, психологии и социологии) зависят от работы друг друга.*

Ключевые слова: *фразеология, фразеологизмы, концепт, лингвокультуремы, номинативные фразеологизмы, коммуникативные фразеологизмы.*

Introduction

A growing number of academics are focusing on the science of phraseology. One of the theories is that phraseological units can be thought of as cultural phenomena, and their functioning can thus be studied in a cultural framework. As a result, phraseology has made its way into the

field of sociolinguistics. We'll look into the cultural identities of English and Uzbek phraseological units in this phase of our research. A stable, consistent collection of words with partially or totally figurative meaning is one of the finest definitions of phraseological units. Phraseological units represent the richness of a language by displaying the cultural paradigms of its speakers. They represent an ethnolinguistic community's cultural archetypes and assist to make apparent the characteristics of its world perspective. In the early twentieth century, linguists focused their emphasis on phraseological units as specific units of language. These word-combinations became the focus of scientific research in the second half of the twentieth century. Main Part In today's modern linguistics the anthropocentric direction, the view of the human factor as an important phenomenon in the study of language, is growing. The linguocognitive, linguopragmatic and linguoculturological aspects of language units are widely studied on the basis of this direction.

One of the main problem to be studied in cognitive linguistics is concept and according to acknowledgement of many researcher's cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology are leading areas of the anthropocentric paradigm. If cognitive linguistics is a science that studies the nature of a particular concept in the linguistic image of the world and its relation to world realities, the concept is one of the leading categories of cognitive linguistics and is an element of communication between culture and humanity. Although the term "concept" has been widely used in linguistics since the 1990s, it still does not have a single explanation or interpretation. Professor G. M. Hoshimov describes the concept as follows: "A concept is the result of not only two important processes, conceptualization and categorization, which are closely related to each other, but also it is an end result of a number of other important processes

It is obvious that phraseological units are closely connected with the spiritual culture, customs, profession, way of life, past, aspirations, attitude to reality of the people who speak the language. In linguistics, course of phraseology is still understood in a broad and narrow sense. Scholars with a broad understanding believe that proverbs, sayings, aphorisms, and other types of fixed units are the components of phraseology. On the other hand, narrow-minded scholars do not evaluate proverbs and sayings as the object of phraseology. According to A.V.Kunin's theory, we support the inclusion of fixed phrases based on the concept of secondary naming, as well as proverbs and sayings, in the list of phraseological Units

We may make the following findings from a comparative examination of samples in English and Uzbek, which belong to separate language families typologically: a) Linguoculturemes are nominative and communicative phraseological units that express the concept of "wedding" in both languages. These units are important in the languages and cultures of the English and Uzbek nations, and it is no exaggeration to say that they are specialized verbal means

for realizing unique ethnolinguistic and linguoculturological features. b) Phraseologisms in the compared languages are distinguished from one another as unique national units – linguoculturemes. In this regard, while their formal properties, i.e. their external structures, are significantly different, they exchange certain semantic components as well as some semantic terminology. For example, certain nominative phraseological units in Uzbek and English; as well as communicative phraseological units in Uzbek and English show that the language and culture of a nation have its own linguoculturological features. Such phraseological units should be given substantial consideration in the teaching and translation processes; otherwise, the ethnolinguistic and linguocultural features of languages may not be highlighted during the study and application process. c). While the resemblance of phraseological verbalizers of the concept of "wedding" in comparable languages may be explained by applying basic rules of language development, their variances can be outlined by its specificity of the thinking of speakers / authors in this or that language

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